

IMPORTANCE OF CONSUMED INSECTS

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Abstract. This article discusses the structure, habitats, stages of development, and role of consumed insects in the production of food products.

Key words: *Tenebrio molitor*, *Hermetia illucens*, protein, fat, optimal temperature.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ПОТРЕБЛЯЕМЫХ НАСЕКОМЫХ

Абстракт. В данной статье рассматриваются строение, места обитания, стадии развития питательных насекомых и их роль в производстве пищевых продуктов.

Ключевые слова: *Tenebrio molitor*, *Hermetia illucens*, белок, жир, оптимальная температура.

Introduction. Considering the growing world population and the consumption demand for protein, sustainable protein production to cover the population needs will be a serious challenge in the future. Edible insects can be a source of protein because they are an efficient source of food with high nutritional value. Insects are a group that exhibits the largest species composition and biological diversity in the animal world and produces a very large biomass in nature [9]. Insects (Latin: Insecta) are invertebrate animals belonging to the arthropod class. About 1.5 million species are known in the world. It occupies the first place in the biosphere in terms of the number of species and variety of forms [6]. There are more than 1,900 species of edible insects on Earth [2].

In world practice, particularly *Musca domestica*, *Hermetia illucens*, *Tenebrio molitor*, *Zophobas atratus*, *Alphitobus diaperinus*, *Galleria mellonella*, *Achroia grisella*, *Bombyx mori*, *Acheta domesticus*, *Grylodes sigillatus*, *Locusta migratoria migratorioides*, *Schistocerca americana* are widely studied in the production of feed products. [5]. Consumed insect (*Tenebrio molitor*) is gaining attention worldwide as a source of protein for food purposes. *Tenebrio molitor* is one of the most widely consumed insects in the world. Food insect larvae contain about 15% fat and 20% protein [10]. In a number of studies, it can also be seen that they contain minerals, vitamins, and fatty acids [8].

Materials and methods. *Tenebrio molitor* is a member of the Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae family and belongs to the family of hard winged beetles. The family of hard-winged beetles is extremely widespread on earth, there are many insects. About 350,000 of their species are known. The thick wings of beetles are strongly chitinized, and the wings that form the tail are thin membrane-like, and are attached under the tail. The bodies of beetles are covered in a strong chitinous covering. Eyes, whiskers and gnawing mouth organs are well developed on the head. The structure of the whiskers has a systematic character.

The developmental stage of *Tenebrio molitor* is divided into 4 stages: egg, larva, pupa and beetle. Their diet is very wide and can feed on organic products, natural decaying leaves, in general all organic products in nature or their residual products. The length of beetles reaches 12-18 mm (Fig. 1). The length of the beetles is up to 2.5 cm and more, brownish-yellow, cylindrical, eyeless, with three pairs of thoracic legs, claws on each leg; whiskers are 4-parted. The back segment of the body is cone-shaped and ends with two hooks directed upwards; the anus is located on a small elevation at the posterior edge of the penultimate segment, and in front of it there are two more small warts - all

of this plays the role of a pusher when the larva moves. *Tenebrio molitor* is distributed everywhere, but its main homeland is the Mediterranean Sea.

The optimum temperature for growing insects is +23-28 °C. Eggs, if necessary, are brought to the required temperature artificially with the help of heaters. Development at +26-28°C takes about 2 weeks. Larvae grow for 4 months. An adult beetle lives 30-45 days [7].

Among the edible insects, *Hermetia illucens* is also a rare insect. Adults and larvae of *Hermetia illucens* are known throughout the world as an excellent feed for poultry, reptiles and fish, being high in calcium and protein. *Hermetia illucens* is known worldwide as a nutritious insect. The length is from 15 to 20 mm. Females are slightly larger than males. The body is completely black. Only the lower legs are white [3]. Larvae are white or yellow, the head is yellow-brown. Body length up to 27 mm. They develop in various decomposing organic matter of plants and animals, including vegetables and fruits, compost, manure, rotten fish, sewage, etc. Mainly found in tropical and subtropical regions. Its homeland is the tropical regions of South America. In recent decades, it has been brought by humans to all continents.

An adult female lays 206 to 639 eggs at a time. Eggs are usually laid in cracks or near rotting material such as manure or compost and hatch in about 4 days. Newly hatched larvae are about 1 mm in diameter and can reach 25 mm in length and 0.10 to 0.22 grams in weight by the end of the larval stage. Larvae can feed on various organic substances and adapt to food with different nutritional content [4]. The larval stage lasts from 18 to 36 days and largely depends on the food it eats. Adults can live from 47 to 73 days if provided with water and food, such as sugar in captivity and nectar in the wild.

Adults live for about 8-10 days on their fat reserves accumulated during the larval stage, if water is provided. Larvae are used as food. This insect is one of the few insect species approved for use as food in many countries. The insect *Hermetia illucens* is grown on an industrial scale as an alternative source of protein and fat for feed and as a raw material for the chemical industry. Insects can also be used to regenerate biomass. *Hermetia illucens* larvae contain 35-40% protein and produce melanin, a natural antioxidant. It is used for feeding farm animals, poultry, and aquatic animals.

Protein and fat storage of some types of nutritious insects.
(relative to dry matter,%)

Types of insects	Scientific name of insects	Protein	Fat
Larvae	<i>Allomyrina dichotoma</i>	54,18	20,24
	<i>Anaphe infracta</i>	20,00	15,20
	<i>Anaphe reticulata</i>	23,00	10,20
	<i>Anaphe venata</i>	25,70	23,21
	<i>Gonimbrasia belina</i>	56,95	10,00
	<i>Gynanisa maja</i>	55,92	12,10
	<i>Protaetia brevitarsis</i>	44,23	15,36
	<i>Rhynchophorus phoenicis</i>	22,06	66,61
	<i>Tenebrio molitor</i>	46,44	32,70
Beetle	<i>Heteroligus meles</i>	38,10	32,01
	<i>Oryctes boas</i>	26,00	1,50

	<i>Rhynchophorus phoenicis</i>	50,01	21,12
	<i>Rhynchophorus phoenicis</i>	28,42	31,40
Grasshopper	<i>Ruspolia differens</i>	44,59	49,00
	<i>Zonocerus variegatus</i>	26,80	3,80
Cricket	<i>Brachytrypes spp.</i>	6,25	2,34
	<i>Gryllus bimaculatus</i>	58,32	11,88
	<i>Teleogryllus emma</i>	55,65	25,14
Termites	<i>Macrotermes bellicosus</i>	20,10	28,20
	<i>Macrotermes falciger</i>	43,26	43,00
	<i>Macrotermes natalensis</i>	22,10	22,50
Bee	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	21,00	12,30
Dragonfly	<i>Aeschna multicolor</i>	54,24	16,72
	<i>Anax sp.</i>	26,22	22,93

Alphitobius diaperinus (*Alphitobius diaperinus*) belongs to the family of beetles belonging to the Tenebrionidae family. *Alphitobius diaperinus* includes four genera worldwide. The feeding bug *Alphitobius diaperinus* is broadly oval in structure, moderately convex, black or brown-black, and usually has about 6 to 11 larval instars.

The color may vary depending on age or the "strain" of the smaller worm. Length is about 5.8 to 6.3 mm. His mustache is densely covered with short blond hairs. The head is deeply elongated in front, and the eyes are also visible. The eggs are about 1.5 mm long, white to yellowish in color, and thin in appearance with slightly rounded tips. Larvae have a segmented body, the tip of the abdomen tapers back, and three pairs of legs. At the last stage, their length is about 7 to 11 mm. Newly emerged larvae have a milky color. A brown shade is observed after the third stage to give a yellowish-brown appearance [1].

Heteroligus meles is widespread in tropical Africa. Adult beetles are 23 - 33 mm long, dark brown to black in color, with 2 visible gans on the head. The beetles lay their eggs in the soil near river banks and feed on grass roots and other organic matter.

Conclusion. One of the global problems facing humanity today is the huge need for food products. This puts before the world scientists the task of providing mankind with ecologically safe food products with full nutritional value. Various biotechnological methods have been put into practice to solve this problem. Cultivation of edible insects and their use as food and feed products is one of the most convenient and low-cost alternatives.

The main reason for this is that these insects store protein and fat in themselves. In our republic, the use of insects as food is being effectively implemented. These consumed insects serve as a non-traditional source of enriching the nutritious and continuous nutritional base of the country's livestock, poultry and fishery industries.

References:

1. Alves LFA, Rohde C, VS Alves. 2005. Patogenicidade de *Steinernema glaseri* va *S.carpocapsae* (Nematoda: Rhabdita) kontra o cascudinho, *Alphitobius diaperinus* (Panzer) (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae). *Neotropik entomologiya* 34: 139-141.

2. Bruno, Daniele; Bonelli, Marco; De Filippis, Francesca; Di Lelio, Ilaria; Tettamanti, Gianluca; Casartelli, Morena; Ercolini, Danilo; Caccia, Silvia (2018-11-30). McBain, Andrew J. (ed.). "The Intestinal Microbiota of *Hermetia illucens* Larvae Is Affected by Diet and Shows a Diverse Composition in the Different Midgut Regions". *Applied and Environmental Microbiology* (англ.). 85
3. Kuppusamy, Giva; Kong, Chee Kei; Segaran, Ganeswaran Chandra; Tarmalingam, Eliyarajan; Herriman, Max; Ismail, Mohd Fathil; Mehmood Khan, Tahir; Low, Liang Ee; Goh, Bey-Hing (2020). "Hummingbird-Leaves-Reared Black Soldier Fly Prepupae: Assessment of Nutritional and Heavy Metal Compositions". *Biology*.
4. Mirzaeva D.A., Khujamshukurov N.A., Zokirov B., Soxibov B.O., Kuchkarova D.Kh. Influence of temperature and humidity on the development of *Tenebrio molitor* l. *Int. J. Curr. Microbiol. App. Sci.* 2020. 9(5):3544-3559. (IP0.54).
5. Mirzaeva D.A. Noan'anaviy manbalar asosida ozuqa yemi olish texnologiyasini ishlab chiqish // *Biologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) dissertatsiyasi avtoreferati*. –Toshkent. 2021. B.-23.
6. Striganova B.R. Zaxarov A.A. Hayvon nomlarining besh tilli lug'ati: Hasharotlar. Lotin, rus, ingliz, nemis, fransuz / ed. biologiya fanlari doktori fanlari, prof. B. R. Striganova. - M.: RUSSO, 2000. - S. 146. - 1060 nusxa.
7. Turabekova, D. B., Khujamshukurov, N. A., & Salomova, S. S. (2024). PHYTOSANITARY CONTROL OF FUSARIUM DISEASE IN VINEYARDS. *SCHOLAR*, 2(4), 4-9.
8. Hazeleger, W. C., et al. (2008). Darkling beetles (*Alphitobius diaperinus*) and their larvae as potential vectors for the transfer of *Campylobacter jejuni* and *Salmonella enterica* serovar Paratyphi B variant Java between successive broiler flocks. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology* 74(22), 6887-91.
9. *Zoologiya* – S.Dadayev, O.Mavlonov Toshkent. 2008.
10. Мирзаева Д.А., Хужамшукуров Н.А., Кучкарова Д.К. *Tenebrio molitor*: protein synthesis. Международная научная конференция молодых учёных и специалистов, посвящённая 160-летию В.А.Михельсона. Сборник статей. Том 1. Москва, РГАУ-МСХА имени К.А.Тимирязева, 2020. -С.146-150.